

The Influence of Work Environment and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance as Mediated by Achievement Motivation

(Case Study at Bureau of Personnel and Organization, Ministry of Village, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration)

Eka Lia Sinuraya¹, Singmin Johannes Lo²
 Postgraduate master's in management
 Mercu Buana University Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the effect of the work environment and organizational culture on employee performance through the mediation of achievement motivation. The research population consists of 64 permanent employees working in the Bureau of Personnel and Organizations, using the Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square with SmartPLS 3.2.9. The result of this study found that the work environment has a direct and significant positive effect on employee performance and achievement motivation; organizational culture has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance; organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on achievement motivation; achievement motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; work environment mediated by achievement motivation has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance; organizational culture by mediating achievement motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Organizational leaders are suggested to improve a conducive office atmosphere and create harmonious relationships among employees so that employee performance increases.

Keywords:- Work Environment, Organization Culture, Achievement Motivation, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, the quality of human resources has become a key to organizational success. Therefore, to achieve effective human resource management that can enhance the organization's effectiveness and efficiency, human resources have become an essential factor in accomplishing the goals of an organization [1].

In the Indonesian government organization, human resources are regulated by Undang-Undang No. 5 Tahun 2014 tentang Aparatur Sipil Negara (ASN), this law stipulated that ASN must be part of bureaucratic reform and have the obligation to manage and develop themselves as part of their responsibility towards their performance. This is done to implement good government management and to reposition themselves to respond to public demand as well as to carry out an adaptive, agile, and fluid bureaucratic transformation strategy.

The personnel and organization Bureau's tasks include coordinating, developing, and providing support for employee development, and administrative management of personal affairs, organizational development, and implementation, as well as facilitating the ministry's bureaucratic reform. To fulfill its task and function, the personnel and organization Bureau must be able to adapt to globalization and bring changes to its systems mechanisms. However, based on the obtained employee performance data, there has been a downward trend in employee performance over there years period, from 2019 to 2021.

Table 1: Employees Job Performance Score of the personnel and organization Bureau between 2019-2021

Years	Total Employees	Element		Total (%)	Target (%)	Information
		SKP (%)	Performance (%)			
2019	60	87,85	92	89,93	100	Not Achieved
2020	60	85,78	84	84,89	100	Not Achieved
2021	61	85,70	84	84,85	100	Not Achieved

The job performance appraisal results indicate The Personnel and Organization Bureau of the Ministry of Village, Disadvantaged Region Development, and Transmigration failed to achieve the organization's targets by 100% during the period from 2019 to 2021. This issue should be the focus that requires the attention of the

organization's leadership as it will have an impact on the organization's performance.

The phenomenon occurs due to the non-conductive working environment, both physically and non-physically, such as less harmonious relation between employees, decreased work motivation caused by organizational

changes, and the lack of awareness and initiative from employees in completing tasks on time.

Based on the result of the first interview by the key person and pre-survey on 25 sample respondents at The Personnel and Organization, it was found that there are symptoms related to the decline in employee performance. Therefore, it become the researcher’s concern to conduct a study related to the issue of employee performance in the Personnel and Organization Bureau.

II. LITERATURE

A. Employee Performance

Performance is the result of work achieved by employees, both in terms of performance quantity, in carrying out their tasks according to the targets and responsibilities assigned by organization [2]. Another opinion suggests that employee performance is an achievement of work, which is compared between the actual work result obtained and the work standards set by the organization [3]. From these definitions, it can be concluded that employee performance is the work result achieved by each employee within a specific time based on the targets set by the organization.

B. Work Environment

The work environment is defined as a place where several groups exist, and within it, there are supporting facilities to achieve the company goal’s according to its vision and mission [4]. Additionally, the work environment is capable of being understood as the overall workplace infrastructure and facilities surrounding employees, where they perform their tasks and influence the execution of work activities. This work environment comprises the workspace, facilities, and work tools. Used, cleanliness, lighting,

tranquility, and even relationship among respondents [5]. Another researcher reveals that work environment, such as social relationships at workplace, become one of main reasons why employees feel satisfied with their organization conditions [6]. From these definitions, it can be concluded that the work environment encompasses the overall work infrastructure surrounding employees, the workspace, methods used, and relationships among respondents to achieve the organization’s goals in line with vision and mission.

C. Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a shared system of meanings embraced by the members to distinguish from other types of organizations [7]. Based on this definition, it can be inferred that organizational culture evolves as it is formed and nurtured by individuals within the organization, and it is embraces as values that should be preserved and transmitted to every new member. These values serve as guidelines for each member throughout their tenure in the organizational setting and can be viewed as unique traits that set one organization apart from other.

D. Achievement Motivation

Motivation is the mental and spiritual state of a person that drives oneself to develop potential to achieve maximum achievement [8]. Motivation is also described as the condition that propels employees to achieve their goals based on their motives. Therefore, motivation is highly necessary to support all organizational activities to become better, as higher motivation will lead employees to contribute their full abilities to the organization [9]. Based on these definitions, we can infer that motivation is the endeavor to achieve success or excellence in competition, surpassing the achievements of others.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Building on the foundation of previous research, the study’s framework is outlined as follows.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

In Accordance with the image provided, this study consists of seven hypotheses, namely:

- H1: Work Environment has a positive and a significant effect on Employee Performance
- H2: Work Environment has a positive and a significant effect on Achievement Motivation

- H3: Organizational Culture has a positive and a significant effect on Employee Performance
- H4: Organizational Culture has a positive and a significant effect on Achievement Motivation
- H5: Achievement Motivation has a positive and a significant effect on Employee Performance

- H6: Work Environment has a positive and a significant effect on Employee Performance as Mediated by Achievement Motivation
- H7: Organizational Culture has a positive and a significant effect on Employee Performance as Mediated by Achievement Motivation.

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this study, a quantitative method was used, which is a scientific method that utilizes numerical data that can be processed and analyzed using statistical techniques [10]. The author sent the questionnaire link through google form. The author distributed to 64 valid respondents for analysis. In analyzing the data, the author used the Partial Least Square – Structural Equation Model (SEM) as the variance-

based analysis tool, using SmartPLS 3.0 to analyze structural models [11].

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The research findings based on work experience show that most of the new employees who work less than 5 years account for 46.9%, while senior employees with work experience exceeding 15 years are 14.1% or 9 employees. The age group predominantly falls within the productive age range of >30-40 years, accounting for 45.3%. As for education, the majority holds a bachelor’s degree, with 68.8% or total of 44 individuals. Meanwhile, in terms of gender, female employees dominate with 57.8%, totaling 37 individuals. these are the findings from the conducted data analysis.

Table 2: Construct Reliability and Validity Result

Variable	Items	Outer Loading	CR	CA	AVE
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE	Y1.2	0.817	0.959	0.953	0.683
	Y1.3	0.830			
	Y2.1	0.713			
	Y2.2	0.866			
	Y2.3	0.851			
	Y3.1	0.806			
	Y3.2	0.810			
	Y3.3	0.885			
	Y4.2	0.802			
	Y4.3	0.859			
WORK ENVIRONMENT	Y5.3	0.753	0.973	0.967	0.857
	X1.1.1	0.959			
	X1.1.2	0.959			
	X1.1.3	0.958			
	X1.2.1	0.961			
	X1.2.2	0.931			
ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE	X1.2.3	0.942	0.954	0.946	0.676
	X2.1.1	0.783			
	X2.1.2	0.785			
	X2.1.3	0.827			
	X2.2.1	0.884			
	X2.2.2	0.928			
	X2.2.3	0.783			
	X2.3.1	0.918			
	X2.3.2	0.920			
	X2.3.3	0.707			
	X2.4.1	0.912			
	X2.4.2	0.951			
	X2.4.3	0.911			
	X2.5.1	0.826			
	X2.5.2	0.832			
	X2.5.3	0.787			
	X2.6.1	0.771			
	X2.6.2	0.920			
	X2.6.3	0.854			
	X2.7.1	0.898			
X2.7.2	0.914				
X2.7.3	0.864				
ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION	Z1	0.927	0.979	0.973	0.904
	Z2	0.933			
	Z4	0.951			
	Z5	0.973			
	Z6	0.940			

The data above indicates has outer loading > 0.70, which can fulfill convergent validity. The Cronbach’s Alpha exceeds 0.7, and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

exceeds 0.5, indicating that all variables are valid and reliable [11].

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker Test Result

	Organizational Culture	Employee Performance	Work Environment	Achievement Motivation
Organizational Culture	0.727			
Employee Performance	0.708	0.770		
Work Environment	0.671	0.758	0.926	
Achievement Motivation	0.696	0.758	0.619	0.904

The table above shows the results of the Fornell-Larcker test, discriminant validity is deemed acceptable when the root average variance extracted (AVE) of all

variables surpasses the correlation value between different constructs. Therefore, the data above fulfills discriminant validity.

Table 5: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Construct Relationships	Path Coefficient	Mean	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistic (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Direct Effect						
Work Environment (X1) -> Employee performance (Y)	0.400	0.396	0.142	2.283	0.005	Significant
Work Environment (X1) -> Achievement Motivation (Z)	0.366	0.391	0.134	2.722	0.007	Significant
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Employee performance (Y)	0.146	0.143	0.117	1.247	0.213	Not Significant
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Achievement Motivation (Z)	0.402	0.378	0.128	3.136	0.002	Significant
Achievement Motivation (Z) -> Employee performance (Y)	0.402	0.410	0.140	2.868	0.004	Significant
Indirect Effect						
Work Environment (X1) -> Achievement Motivation (Z) -> Employee performance (Y)	0.147	0.162	0.084	1.754	0.080	Not Significant
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Achievement Motivation (Z) -> Employee performance (Y)	0.162	0.154	0.075	2.145	0.032	Significant
Total Effect						
Organizational Culture (X2) -> Achievement Motivation (Z) -> Employee performance (Y)	0.308	0.307	0.114	2.700	0.007	Significant

The hypothesis testing results show that there is positive and significant influence of the work environment (X1) on employee performance (Y). The evaluation of the inner model shows a t-statistic value of 2.283 > t-statistic table of 1.979; and a P-Value of 0.005 < 0.05, and the coefficient value is positive at 0.400, indicating that the work environment variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance variable (Y). Thus, the hypothesis 1 in this study, which states that “There is a positive and significant influence of the work environment on employee performance, is accepted”. These finding align with previous studies that have discovered a

positive and significant correlation between the work environment on employee performance [12]. However, in contrast to other studies that found the workplace environment to have a non-significant effect on employee performance [13].

The hypothesis testing indicates there is positive and significant influence of the work environment (X1) on achievement motivation (Z). The evaluation of the inner model shows a t-statistic value of 2.722 > t-statistic table of 1.979.

Table 4: Coefficient of determination (R²)

	R Square
Employee Performance	0.687
Achievement Motivation	0.478

The table above show the interrelations between constructs based in R square. It can be explained that the employee performance variable (Y) has a value of 0.687, indicating that 68.8% of the employee performance can be influenced by the work environment (X1) and organizational culture (X2), the rest 31.3% is affected by other variables not examined. Furthermore, the interrelation between construct based on R square in the achievement motivation variable (Z) is 0.478. This indicated that 47.8% of the achievement motivation variable can be influenced by work environment (X1) and organizational culture (X2), while the remaining 52.2% is influenced by other variables not examined.

P-Value of $0.007 < 0.05$, and the coefficient value is positive at 0.366, indicating that the work environment variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on achievement motivation variable (Z). Therefore, the hypothesis 2 in this study regarding, "There is a positive and significant influence of the work environment on achievement motivation, is accepted". These finding are consistent with previous researcher's results, where they found a positive and significant relationship between the work environment and work motivation [14], but contrast from the findings of other researchers who reported that the work environment has a positive but non-significant influence on work motivation [15].

The next hypothesis indicates there is a positive but not significant influence of organizational culture (X2) on employee performance (Y). The inner model evaluation shows in a t-statistic value of $1.247 < 1.979$; and a P-Value of $0.213 > 0.05$, and the coefficient value shows a positive effect of 0.146, indicating that the organizational culture (X2) has a positive but not significant impact on employee performance (Y). Therefore, the hypothesis 3 of this study, stating that the positive and significant influence of organizational culture affects employee performance, "is rejected.". these findings are supported by previous research that found a positive but non-significant influence of organizational culture on employee performance [16]. But contrast with other researchers results that reported a significant influence of organizational culture on employee performance [17].

The hypothesis testing results indicate that there is positive and significant influence of organizational culture (X2) on achievement motivation (Z). The inner model evaluation shows a t-statistic value of $3.136 > 1.979$; and a P-Value of $0.002 < 0.05$, and the coefficient value is positive at 0.402, meaning that the organizational culture variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on achievement motivation (Z). The hypothesis H4 of this study, which is the positive and significant influence of organizational culture on achievement motivation," is accepted. This research aligns with previous studies where organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on motivation [14], and contrast with research indicating that organizational culture does not have a significant influence on motivation [18].

Hypothesis H5 indicates that there is positive and significant influence of achievement motivation (Z) on employee performance (Y). The inner model evaluation shows a t-statistic value of $2.868 > 1.979$; and a P-Value of $0.004 < 0.05$, and the coefficient value is positive at 0.402, meaning that the achievement motivation (Z) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y). Therefore, the hypothesis H5 of this study, stating that "there is a positive and significant influence of achievement motivation on employee performance," is accepted. This research is supported by previous studies that found a positive and significant influence of motivation on employee performance [19][20], while other researchers obtained contrasting results, indicating that motivation indirectly affects employee performance in a negative manner [21].

Furthermore, regarding hypothesis H6, which suggests a positive but non-significant of the work environment (X1) on employee performance (Y) through the mediation of achievement motivation (Z). The inner model evaluation shows a t-statistic value of $1.754 < 1.979$; and a P-Value of $0.080, > 0.05$. Meanwhile, the coefficient value shows a positive effect with a value of 0.147, indicating that the work environment (X1) has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance (Y) through the mediation of achievement motivation (Z). Therefore, the hypothesis H6 of this study, stating that "there is a positive and significant influence of the work environment on employee performance through the mediation of achievement motivation," is rejected. This research contradicts previous studies where the work environment, through motivation, was found to have a significant relationship with job performance [14].

This hypothesis demonstrates the positive and significant influence of organizational culture (X2) on employee performance (Y) through the mediation of achievement motivation (Z). The inner model shows a t-statistic value of $2.145 > 1.979$; and a P-Value of $0.032 < 0.05$. Additionally, the coefficient value shows a positive value at 0.162. Therefore, the hypothesis H7 of this study, "there is a positive and significant influence of the organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through the mediation of achievement motivation," is accepted. These findings are consistent with previous researchers [22]. While other researchers obtained different results, suggesting that motivation does not affect the relationship between organizational culture and performance [23].

Based on the total affect values, the path coefficient of organizational culture on employee performance from the direct path coefficient of 0.146, combined with the indirect effect 0.162, results in a total effect value of 0.308. this means that if organizational culture increases by one unit, employee performance will also increase both directly and indirectly through the mediation of achievement motivation, and this influence is also positive.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the findings and discussions regarding the human resource issues in the Personnel and Organization Bureau, Ministry of Village, Disadvantaged Regions Development, and Transmigration, the following conclusions can be drawn. The work environment has a positive and significant influence on the employee performance of the Personnel and Organization Bureau. This means that a conducive work environment, including both the physical aspects such as temperature and air circulation, will create comfort for the employees to perform their tasks. As a result, it will affect the employee's performance in the Personnel and Organization Bureau.

The work environment has a positive and significant influence on the achievement motivation of the Personnel and Organization Bureau. This indicates that by improving the office environment with suitable temperature and air circulation, it can support and provide comfort to assist employees in performing their tasks, which in turn will boost their work enthusiasm and drive them to achieve more. Therefore, with a better and conducive work environment, the employee's work motivation will be higher.

The organizational culture has a positive but not significant influence on the employee performance of the Personnel and Organization Bureau, indicating that the employees have not managed to adapt to the changes taking place in the organization. These changes might be perceived by employees as being too forced, resulting in the existing organizational culture not effectively contributing to improving their performance.

The achievement motivation is positively and significantly influenced by the organizational culture, meaning that the leadership of the Bureau must continuously provide encouragement to employees to prove their work achievements. By attention to every result and accomplishment of the employees, the leadership can enhance the motivation of the employees to excel further in their performance.

Achievement motivation has a positive and significant influence on the employee performance of the Personnel and Organization Bureau. This means that if achievement motivation is instilled among all employees, it will be able to enhance their performance. Therefore, the leadership of the Bureau is expected to provide encouragement and enthusiasm to the employees to initiate in their work. Additionally, this motivation will drive the employees to perform their tasks even better than before.

Based on the analysis and conclusions above, it is suggested as follows:

- The leadership of the Personnel and Organization Bureau is advised to provide instructions to the administration to improve the office space to be more conducive by considering the needs of air circulation, room temperature, and supporting facilities for the comfort of the employees while working.

- The leadership should focus on internalizing the organizational culture to all employees, which will cultivate a sense of motivation in achieving their work targets. This will subsequently lead to greater job satisfaction among employees with regards to their work achievements.
- The leadership should also work on improving the organizational stability and placing a high value on consistency and adherence to rules and regulations. Any organizational change should be carefully planned and aligned with the organization's mission. Furthermore, they should enhance and encourage employee's work enthusiasm to the initiatives in carrying out their tasks. This can be achieved through activities such as focus group discussions (FGD), seminars with competent speakers, and gatherings involving all employees to provide opportunities for listening to their aspirations and showcasing abilities.
- The leadership should conduct evaluations on employees' performance targets to assess each employee's capabilities in fulfilling their tasks effectively according to expectations. By implementing such evaluations, employees will foster a sense of responsibility in accomplishing every work target assigned to them.
- This study still has limitations that are expected to be addressed in future research, such as the relatively small size of only 64 individuals. Which may not fully represent the general population. Subsequent studies can improve the research model by expanding the population and sample variations, thus providing more meaningful and beneficial insights for the organization. In further research focusing on employee performance, it is recommended to explore the influence on other independent variables, such as employee engagement, work discipline, leadership style, self-efficacy, competency, compensation, and other variables, to predict their impact on employee performance.

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